

Comparative Analysis between Family Variables and Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Ondo Metropolis, Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study comparative analysis between family variables and sexual behaviour among secondary school students. Descriptive Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of all secondary school students in Ondo metropolis during the 2023/2024 academic session. The sample comprised three hundred (300) students randomly selected from six (6) schools in the metropolis. Questionnaire on Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students (QSBSSS) was used to collect data. Reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach's Alpha statistics which yielded a coefficient of 0.82. Data collected was analysed using ANOVA and t-test. The results revealed that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type ($F = 2.902, p > 0.05$). The findings showed that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's occupation while there is in that of mother's occupation ($t = 1.084, p > 0.05$) and $t = 4.038, p < 0.05$) respectively. It was also revealed that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification while there is in that of mother's qualification ($F = 0.730, p > 0.05$ and $F = 1.495, p < 0.05$ respectively). It was concluded that mothers are found to be of more important figures than father in influencing sexual behaviour of secondary school students, it was therefore recommended that parents should be involved in organising sex education programme for secondary school students and workshops on sexuality education should be organised for parents to have more idea and exposure on what to teach their children.

Keywords: Sexual behaviour, family variables, adolescents

Introduction

Sexual behaviour is an aspect of sexuality which deals with expression of sexual feelings. Hyde and Delamater (2003) asserted that sexual behaviour is that behaviour that produces sexual arousal and increases the chances of orgasm. Adolescence or youthful period is the most remarkable and troublesome when it comes to the issue of sexual behaviour. The reason for this is that at the period, because of the pubertal changes and increase in the secretion of sex hormones in the body, many young people tend to experiment with sex. This experimentation exposes them to different sexually related problems such as STIs and HIV/AIDS, unplanned pregnancy, abortion and complications associated with it, disrupted future, psychological trauma, and so on.

According to Modebelu (2010), sexual behaviour is any activity (including kissing, pecking, necking, hugging, coital relationship, anal and oral sex and also masturbation) in varying degree and forms which satisfies one's sexual desires and urges. An individual may have positive or negative sexual behaviour. Positive or healthy sexual behaviour includes the ability to suspend the onset of sexual intercourse, making right choices of partners when the time comes, having limited number, at least one sexual partner when sexually active, sexual absenteeism, or proper use of condom if already sexually active and active protection of one's self against sexual harassment (McKay, 1993). On the other hand, risky or negative sexual behaviour is exposure of oneself to risky sexual activities without control over one's sexual activities (Cohen & Trussel, 1996). Modebelu (2010) opined that negative sexual behaviour is being careless in the use of one's sexuality and also undue exposure of one's self to sexual risk. Puente and Zabaleta (2011) reported that the period of adolescence concedes with a surge of sexual interest which results from such factors as physical body change, hormonal increase, increase in social emphasis on sex and the adolescent's necessary rehearsal for adult roles. These changes propel the intense preoccupation with sexual exploration and experimentation. These sex-crazed and hormone-driven individuals get involved in a lot of high-risk sexual behaviour which are detrimental to them, their families and the society.

Young people's sexual behavior have been noted to be influenced by a number of factors such as sexuality education, sexual knowledge, type of family and neighbourhood (Adegoke, 2004). Over the past two decades, there has been a large body of research substantiating the powerful influence of the family on adolescent sexual health behaviours outcomes (Simpson, 2001). In general, studies found that adolescents in married, biological two – parent families are less likely to engage in unprotected sex and early sexual initiation compared to adolescents from single parent, cohabiting stepfather, and married stepfather families (Wu & Thompson, 2001). Babalola, Tambashe and Vondrasek (2005) asserted that irrespective of whether it is a low, middle or high – income country, adolescents raised in single parent households have an increased probability of both early sexual debut and pregnancy. In the same vein, Kingori and Kingoru (2016) emphasized the fact that father's absence may cause adolescent daughters to have difficulties relating to other males; these difficulties may take different forms for daughters of widows and divorcees. Adolescent girls from divorced homes appeared to be more sexually preconscious and assertive with males, whereas those whose mothers were widowed were characterized as excessively anxious about sexuality and as shy and uncomfortable around males. Daughters learn to feel competent and to value and acquire the social skills necessary for effective heterosexual interactions by interacting with warm, responsive, masculine fathers, who reward and enjoy their daughters' femininity.

Considering the role of family as agent of socialisation for children and adolescents, there is a need to investigate the influence of family variables (such as family type, father's and mother's occupation and qualification) on adolescents' sexual behaviour, so as to come up with counselling intervention to mitigate their risky sexual behaviour.

Objectives of the Study

This study was designed to:

1. Find out the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type.
2. Investigate the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's occupation.
3. Examine the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's occupation.
4. Determine the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification.
5. Investigate the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's qualification.

Research Hypotheses

To guide the conduct of the study, the following research hypotheses were raised.

1. There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type.
2. There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's occupation.
3. There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's occupation.
4. There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification.
5. There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's qualification.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted to examine family variables and sexual behaviour among secondary school students. The population consisted of all secondary school students in Ondo metropolis. The sample comprised three hundred (300) students randomly selected from six (6) schools in the metropolis. Self-developed structured questionnaire titled "Questionnaire on Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students (QSBSSS)" was used as instrument for the study. The questionnaire was divided into two sections (A & B). Section A was on personal data of the respondents while section B consisted of items on students' sexual behaviour with four Likert type scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach's Alpha statistics which yielded a co-efficient of 0.82. Data collected was analysed using t-test and ANOVA.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type. In testing this hypothesis, the respondents were classified into three groups based on family type (monogamy, polygamy and others) and scores on sexual behaviour were analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: One-way Analysis of Variance summary of the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	60.450	3	20.150	2.902	.820
Within Groups	17306.052	296	58.466		
Total	17366.502	299			

From Table 1, the mean squares between groups and within groups are 60, 450 and 17306.052 respectively. These yielded the F-value of 2.902 which is not significant at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on family type.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's occupation.

In testing this hypothesis, the respondents were classified into two groups based on father's occupation (i.e. self-employed or civil servant) and scores on sexual behaviour were analysed using t-test. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Independent t-test of the difference in the sexual behaviour of students based on father's occupation

Variable	N	Mean	St.D	df	t	Sig.	P
Sexual behaviour	252	26.99	4.916	298	1.084	.471	>.05
	48	28.01	4.173				

As shown in Table 2, students whose fathers are self-employed have a mean score of 26.99 and a standard deviation of 4.916 while students whose fathers are civil servants have a mean score of 28.01 and a standard deviation of 4.173. A t-test analysis of these values yielded a t-value of 1.084 which is not significant at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students whose fathers are self-employed and civil servants.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's occupation.

In testing this hypothesis, the subjects were grouped into two based on mother's occupation (self-employed and civil servant) and scores on sexual behaviour were analysed using t-test. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Independent t-test of the difference in the sexual behaviour of students based on mothers occupation

Variable	N	Mean	St.D	df	t	Sig.	P	η^2
Sexual behaviour	275	36.30	3.725	298	4.038	.000	<.05	0.0519
	25	27.18	3.001					

Table 3 shows that students whose mothers are self-employed have a mean score of 36.30 and a standard deviation of 3.725 while those whose mothers are civil servants have a mean score of 27.18 and a standard deviation of 3.001. A t-test analysis of these values yielded a t-value of 4.038 which is significant at 0.05 level. This implies that there is significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students whose mothers are self-employed and civil servants Size of effect ($\eta^2 = 0.0519$) reveals that mother's occupation had low effect (according to Cohen 1988 and Field, 2000 rule of thumb for size of effect) on sexual behaviour of secondary school students; that is, mother's occupation accounted for 5.19% change in the sexual behaviour of students.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification.

In testing this hypothesis, subjects were grouped into six based on the father's qualification and scores on sexual behaviour were analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: One-way Analysis of Variance summary of the difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	472.811	4	118.203	0.730	.711
Within Groups	25449.147	295	86.268		

Total 17910.560 299

As shown in Table 4, the mean squares between groups and within groups are 472.811 and 25449.147 respectively. These yielded the F-value of 0.730 which is not significant at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on father's qualification.

Hypothesis Five: There is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's qualification.

In testing this hypothesis, respondents were classified into six groups based on mother's qualification and scores on sexual behaviour were analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance summary of the difference in the sexual behaviour of students based on mother's qualification

Source of Variable	N	$\bar{\chi}$	St.D	df	SS	MS	F	Sig.	P	W ²	η^2
Primary six		11.20	4.008	5	738.118	147.624	1.495	.000	<0.05	0.0428	0.00742
SSCE		24.22	6.173	294	29025.037	98.725					
NCE/OND		17.04	4.850								
HND/B.Sc.		22.53	2.171								
M.Sc.		16.92	4.116								
Ph.D		18.00	3.824								
Total	300	18.32	3.68	299	29,763.155						

Source: Field, 2023.

From Table 5, the mean squares between groups and within groups are 738.118 and 29025.037 respectively. These yielded the F-value of 1.495 which is significant at 0.05 level. This implies that there is a significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students based on mother's qualification. The size of effect ($w^2=0.0428$) reveals that mother's qualification had low effect on the sexual behaviour of secondary school students. This is, qualification of the respondents mothers accounted for 4.28% variance in the sexual behaviour of secondary school students.

Discussion of Findings

This study showed that there is no significant difference in the sexual behaviour of secondary school based on family type (monogamous, polygamous and others). This is supported by Oluwatosin (2010) who found that family type does not significantly influence risky sexual behaviour among undergraduate students. Contrary to this, Laddunuri (2013) reported that family structure (polygamous and separated) as a whole is a significant factor in which students from polygamous and separated family engage in sexual intercourse 1.965 and 2.07 times higher than that of the students from monogamous family respectively. In their study, Kushal et. al., (2022) found that parental monitoring rather than parental support had strong influence on decreasing the odds of having early sexual debut among adolescents. While family structure has been suggested to have an indirect effect on adolescent sexual behaviour, parent-child interactions and processes are believed to have a more direct effect on such behaviour (Defo & Dimbuene, 2012).

The results of the study revealed that father's occupation has no significant influence on sexual behaviour of the secondary school students while mother's occupation has. This implies that sexual behaviour of students whose fathers are self-employed is not significantly different from those whose fathers are civil servants while sexual behaviour of students whose mothers are self-employed is significantly different from those whose mothers are civil servants. A possible explanation for this is in gender-stereotyping in which mothers are expected to create more time than fathers in nurturing their children. They are expected to be at home more than fathers who are using almost all their time in fending for the family. That is why fathers presence at home may not be as significant as that of the mothers in guiding the children. The significant influence of mother's occupation on sexual behaviour of secondary school students may be based on the fact that a self-employed mother may not be able to predict her time-table for the day. Business opportunity may come anytime which would disrupt the time she could spend at home. On the other hand, civil servant mother could plan her time on monitoring, communicating and relating with her children especially the adolescents, which would in turn impact on their sexual behaviour. According to Bonell et. al. (2006), girls and boys from lone parents families or having mothers who were teenagers when they were born were more likely to report sex but not lack of contraception at first sex by age 15/16. Girls and boys with mothers having them as teenagers, and boys but not girls from lone parent families, were more likely to report being involved in contraception by age 15/16.

The study also found that father's qualification has no significant influence on sexual behaviour of secondary school students while mother's qualification has. Laddunuri (2013) found that education of mother and sexual intercourse were significantly associated with each other. And also, in the case of education of father and intercourse were significantly associated. The teens from families where fathers have less education are more likely to be sexually active than teens who come from families where fathers have more education. This relationship is pretty linear to and proxy between rates of sexual activity and level of father's education. The higher the father's education the less likely the teen is to be sexually active (Dryfoos, 1990).

Conclusion

Mothers are found to be of more important figure than fathers in influencing sexual behaviour of secondary school students. There is a need for contemporary career mother to find means of balancing their time in building relationship with their children for position sexual behaviour among the adolescents.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Parents should be involved in organising sex education programmes for secondary school students.
2. All available avenues should be used in encouraging parent-child communication on sexuality.
3. Parent – Teacher Association meetings should be used as avenue to sensitize parents on the importance of educating their children on sexuality.
4. Workshops on sexuality education should be organised for parents to have more idea and exposure on what to teach their children.
5. School counsellors should be on alert to identify students who need individual and parental attention for counselling intervention.
6. Counsellors should identify students who lack parental support due to their family background for in-depth group counselling on sexuality.

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